

NASA Science Mission Directorate Data Repositories Workshop 2023 Informal Report

16 May 2024

This document is not an official NASA report, but it was reviewed by the NASA SMD Repository Standards and Guidelines Working Group, the Workshop Program Committee, and the breakout group leaders.

CONTENTS

Introduction and Summary	4
Summary of Findings.....	4
Day 1	6
Session 1 — Introductions, Framing the Meeting, Background, and Work in Progress.....	6
Welcome from CIRES/NSIDC — Waleed Abdalati (University of Colorado, Boulder).....	6
Opening Remarks — Kevin Murphy (NASA OCSDO).....	6
Code of Conduct and How Things Will Work — Molly Adams (NASA OCSDO).....	7
SPD-41a and its Impact on Repositories — Steve Crawford (NASA OCSDO).....	7
Background and Purpose of the Workshop — Mark Parsons (NASA OCSDO; University of Alabama, Huntsville).....	8
Networking exercise — Led by Mark Parsons (NASA OCSDO; University of Alabama, Huntsville).....	9
SDE and SciX Collaboration — Alberto Accomazzi (Smithsonian Astrophysical Observatory), Emily Foshee and Ashish Acharya (University of Alabama, Huntsville).....	9
Update on Core Services — Elena Steponaitis (NASA OCSDO) and.....	10
Andrew Mitchell (NASA OCSDO).....	10
Data Sharing Guidance for Researchers — Rachel Paseka (NASA OCSDO).....	11
Session 2 — Breakouts.....	12
SDE/SciEx — Led by Elena Steponaitis (NASA OCSDO).....	12
Access in the Cloud — Led by Andrew Mitchell (NASA OCSDO).....	12
Researcher Submitted Data — Led by Rachel Paseka (NASA OCSDO).....	13
Licenses — Led by Steve Crawford (NASA OCSDO).....	15
Identity Management — Led by Elena Steponaitis and Andrew Mitchell (NASA OCSDO). 16	
Streamlining Metadata Generation and Curation — Led by Rebecca Ringuette (NASA Goddard Space Flight Center) and Anne Raugh (University of Maryland).....	17
Day 2	18
Session 1 — The Principles in Detail.....	18
Defining Roles and Incentives for Providers and Repositories — Led by Anne Raugh (University of Maryland) and Bob Downs (Columbia University).....	19
FAIR Assessment Tools — Led by Rebecca Ringuette (NASA GSFC Heliophysics Digital Resource Library) and Ge Peng (UAH/MSFC IMPACT).....	20
Schema.org Training Session — Led by Ruth Duerr.....	21
Session 2 — User Engagement.....	21
Efforts to Understand Users in the Divisions.....	21
User Panel.....	22
Day 3	24
Unconference.....	24
FAIR for Software.....	25
Sharing of Experiments or Works in Progress.....	25
Large Language Models for Curation.....	26

Lowering Barriers and Ensuring Equitable Access to Cloud Computing and Big Data on Demand.....	27
Closing.....	28
Acknowledgements.....	28
Appendix — Post workshop survey results.....	30

Introduction and Summary

The [Office of the Chief Science Data Officer](#) (OCSDO), at NASA's Science Mission Directorate (SMD), conducts annual workshops to coordinate and inform the work of NASA's science data repositories. The [2023 workshop](#) was held 27-29 September in Boulder, Colorado. It was hosted by the National Snow and Ice Data Center and organized by the OCSDO and the Repository Standards and Guidelines Working Group (WG). This report provides a summary of the results of that workshop.

The theme of the 2023 workshop was “FAIR for NASA data.” FAIR is the broadly recognized acronym, which refers to [15 principles](#) that help make data “findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable.”

The workshop goals were to:

- Improve understanding and align interpretation of the specific [15 FAIR principles](#) in the NASA context.
- Identify areas of collaborative and integrated effort for adhering to the principles (e.g., governance processes) and where more work is needed; begin to lay out a roadmap.
- Identify where to develop common guidelines for key FAIR practices such as identifiers and licenses for data.
- Identify consistent and effective means of user engagement since it is the users who ultimately decide if data are FAIR.

To set the stage for the workshop, the working group conducted a survey of the NASA repositories on their FAIR practices and hosted two webinars highlighting examples of FAIR practice within and external to NASA. Links to the planning survey results and webinars are available at <https://science.data.nasa.gov/news/events-fair-for-nasa-data/>.

The first day of the workshop included updates on work in progress and breakouts designed to get community feedback. The first half of the second day focused on the technical details of what repositories can do to make their data FAIR. This contributes to a developing guidance document: [“How to Make NASA Science Data more FAIR”](#). The second half of day 2 addressed how repositories can engage their users and understand what FAIR means to them. Day three was an unconference with topics defined by the participants at the time. Unconference topics included FAIR for software, sharing works in progress, large language models for curation, and providing large data volumes on demand. An appendix shows the results of a post-workshop participant survey.

Summary of Conclusions

Many of the sessions produced concrete conclusions that should inform future work, as well as additions in the “How To” document. Following is a consolidation and summary of the key conclusions.

- General Opportunities:
 - Anyone can apply to [ROSES-23 Amendment 5: F.15 High Priority Open-Source Science](#) to help address issues raised.
 - An increasingly wide range of experience and skill sets will be needed for accessing data. Enhanced documentation (metadata), interfaces, and user education must be an ongoing priority to increase accessibility to the data (see user engagement session).
 - How to handle researcher-submitted data still needs to be defined for different situations while also automating where possible.
- Conclusions for the Standards WG and Repositories
 - Form a task group to create an SMD-wide FAIR metric that enables formal automated assessment and simplifies the creation of FAIR data and metadata. The “How To” document is a starting point but will need more detail.
 - Develop (or codify) guidance for PIDs for model output (see F1 in the “How To” document).
 - Encourage all NASA data repositories to adopt a Levels of Service plan, possibly similar to that followed by [Earth Science](#), to guide how much effort should be spent to make a given dataset FAIR.
 - Develop a metadata coordination group to agree on shared standards and best practices to make the SDE work well and to adhere to federal requirements; develop ongoing improvement practices and tools; coordinate with external entities, etc. (See F2 and I2).
- Opportunities for the OCSDO:
 - Create a forum for sharing repository and user experiences that allows general and more targeted discussions such as how to effectively use the cloud.
 - Collaborate with the data repositories to identify an infrastructure to support research data, especially contributed in support of publications, possibly through a partnership with Zenodo.
 - Identify Large Language Model activity across the divisions. Then build on existing efforts to foster coordination and communication across the activities and data repositories.
 - Present an informational webinar on data and software licensing.
 - Consider developing documented norms for use with Creative Commons Zero (CC0).
 - Create a task group and conduct a workshop on how to make software FAIR.
 - Support a solicitation to fund specific instances of collaboration between data repositories.
 - Make a greater effort to reach a much wider part of the community with RFIs (or other community engagement efforts) everywhere from early to late career researchers. Text should be more clear and more attention should be paid to reach minority and other under-represented communities in RFI responses.

A [very high-level summary](#) of this work was presented as a poster at the 2023 American Geophysical Union Conference. The [full agenda, slides, and notes](#) from the meeting are also available.

Day 1

Session 1 — Introductions, Framing the Meeting, Background, and Work in Progress

The morning kicked off with introductory talks by the host and organizers, delivered to all the attendees.

Welcome from CIRES/NSIDC — Waleed Abdalati (University of Colorado, Boulder)

Waleed remembered his early years at the University of Colorado at Boulder and CIRES (Cooperative Institute for Research in Environmental Sciences), which houses NSIDC (National Snow and Ice Data Center), and how much data he thought they stored, yet how small that amount is, even compared to what is produced today by observation missions on a regular basis. The NSIDC, as one of NASA's DAACs (Distributed Active Archive Centers), is successfully storing and distributing data to researchers to fully realize the value of Earth observing, and other data gathering missions. He is proud of the work the center performs and is delighted to host this meeting on FAIR data.

[Session notes](#)

Opening Remarks — Kevin Murphy (NASA OCSDO)

Kevin reminded the audience (a majority of whom were representatives of repositories) that it was their hard work that shared NASA mission data to scientists so they could perform their research. He reminisced about his early days as a graduate student in remote sensing, and how difficult it was to find and retrieve data from the DAACs, and what a long way they had come since then.

The introduction of SPD-41a requires both data users and providers to evolve how they deal with data, and this meeting is part of that evolution process. It is important for the repositories to listen to each other and to the communities they serve, and the OCSDO encourages and enables this by organizing this workshop, now on a yearly basis during the last week of September.

[Session notes](#)

Code of Conduct and How Things Will Work — Molly Adams (NASA OCSDO)

Molly reminded the participants that we strive to create a friendly, safe, welcoming open culture regardless of race, gender, orientation or creed. If anyone feels the need, they can contact a workshop organizer.

Molly went over workshop logistics, tech requirements, etc.

[Session notes](#)

SPD-41a and its Impact on Repositories — Steve Crawford (NASA OCSDO)

Steve presented *What have we learned* in the process of creating SPD-41a. Most importantly, most groups are already fully (or almost) compliant with it. The core purpose of SPD-41a is to enable researchers to do science and remove burdens. The Science Discovery Engine (SDE) extends NASA's data catalog, and we'll hear more about it in a later session. We analyzed ROSES awards and found that most produce less than 1TB of data, but a few, especially those performing modeling, produce tens to hundreds of TB, and we will need to discuss with the modeling community how to decide what data is useful to share and what should be archived. The biggest ask from researchers has been for guidance in how to implement SDP-41a, which has led to the development of the [Open-Source Science Guidance](#) document for researchers, [openly developed on GitHub](#). We would like to develop similar guidelines for data repositories.

Steve highlighted that 2023 is [A Year of Open Science](#), with NASA [TOPS](#) (Transform to Open Science) carrying out activities to promote it, while also working on a 5-module Open Science course for researchers, which will award badges to those who complete it. At the end of the workshop, those who wish can attend the first module: The Ethos of Open Science.

Steve concluded by highlighting how SPD-41a aims to bring the NASA science community together in making data more FAIR. NASA does a great job in supporting open practices and open data, but it could still do more as it strives to bring more people to its scientific data.

Answering questions:

- Steve pointed out that the Earth Science community had created [a rubric for its community to assess how to handle modeling data](#). Each Division has its own needs and it's time to start having discussions on this matter.
- Beyond making NASA science data FAIR, making it *analysis ready* depended on missions, not just repositories.
- NASA's SMD has been in discussions with CERN to make NASA research data deposited in Zenodo more findable and accessible, ideally through NASA search portals. The process is ongoing.

[Session notes](#)

Background and Purpose of the Workshop — Mark Parsons (NASA OCSDO; University of Alabama, Huntsville)

Mark started off by asking *What is FAIR, what does it really mean?* There are 15 FAIR principles, which are all technical, but how do repositories get there? The workshop organizing committee conducted two webinars leading up to the workshop, and sent out a survey to the repositories on FAIR matters; 68% of repositories replied.

Key findings from this survey were:

- All SMD repositories are working on FAIR, though its meaning varies across repositories.
- Many are using community standards.
- Ten repositories have assessed their use of persistent identifiers.
- There are not necessarily machine-readable licenses in the metadata for their data.

Takeaways from the webinars were:

- Open data and FAIR data are not the same thing.
- FAIR is programmatic and primarily about machine readability.
- FAIRness is a spectrum, and it can apply in slightly different ways across NASA's Science Divisions due to the different needs and requirements of each discipline.
- FAIRness is a journey, not a destination.

At the end of the day, it's the user who determines whether data or a repository are FAIR. Measuring FAIRness has progressed and improved over the years. The [USGS State of the Data project](#) is a comprehensive FAIRness assessment of USGS data started in 2020. One of the key findings is that 70% is the median FAIRness of their data. FAIRness is largely about the metadata. Until we have standard metadata structure, templates, controlled guidelines, and the technology to fill out these templates, we will not be FAIR. The goal is we want data to be born FAIR.

Mark pointed out that we would not be discussing money during the workshop, though he acknowledged that it is an issue in increasing the FAIRness of data at the repositories.

The two perspectives we wish to address are: The users and the machines. We want to improve adherence to the 15 principles, and the goal of the workshop is to produce guidance for repositories in how to accomplish that. In addition, we want to develop recommended practices for engaging users and hearing their needs.

Answering questions:

What is the difference between the [Science Discovery Engine](#) (SDE) and other search/discovery repositories like [data.nasa.gov](#), [data.gov](#), NASA's **CMR (Common Metadata Repository), etc. ?**

The Goal is for SDE to be better than data.gov. More tailored to scientific and related inquiry.

Given that FAIR principles are technology-agnostic, shouldn't we consider defining "Interoperability" at a more granular level since it is best defined along a spectrum from syntactic to semantic capabilities?

Yes, but that is tricky. The 'I' is the hardest principal in the FAIR acronym, harder than 'R'. It will likely be more disciplinary specific but we can start with the basics.

[Session notes](#)

Networking exercise — Led by Mark Parsons (NASA OCSDO; University of Alabama, Huntsville)

The in-person and virtual participants paired off in successive short meetings to discuss what they wished to get out of the workshop and learn what each person's background was.

SDE and SciX Collaboration — Alberto Accomazzi (Smithsonian Astrophysical Observatory), Emily Foshee and Ashish Acharya (University of Alabama, Huntsville)

Alberto presented NASA SciX (Science Explorer), the evolution of the [SAO/NASA ADS](#) (Astrophysics Data System). It is a scientific literature portal, to be unveiled officially at the 2023 AGU meeting in December. It has content and features covering all the disciplines within SMD. It's been 30 years since ADS was developed. Links to data products are indexed for easier discovery, and SciX will provide research content which is aggregated, connected, and indexed for each NASA Division. The core literature for Planetary Science and Heliophysics has been completely ingested, and a census has been completed to determine what Earth Science literature to ingest. Moving forward, collections will continue to be built up, Earth Science materials will continue to be ingested.

Emily and Ashish presented NASA's Science Discovery Engine (SDE). The SDE will enable rapid discovery of NASA science data, software, and documentation. SDE contains more than 84k datasets, 530k documents. The UI has been updated. New icons to represent different divisions of science have been added. Dataset landing pages have been updated to match the schema of [NASA's CMR](#) (Common Metadata Repository), [SPASE](#) (Space Physics Archive Search and Extract), and [PDS3-4](#) (Planetary Data System 3 and 4). The curation workflow goes as follows: Identify source, assess source, create connector, pre-indexing workflows, then post-indexing workflow. A relevance test set was developed to understand changing search results while developing the SDE. Researchers should be able to use this within Jupyter Notebooks and third-party applications. API documentation is in Swagger.

SciX and SDE Collaboration: The main goal is to avoid duplication. The SDE team wants structured metadata, tools related to NASA science data workflows, and supporting documentation. The two systems have been integrated to allow interoperability. An SDE filter is being worked on. Document level metadata is being worked on.

Answering questions:

Question: For SciEx, will data and software only be linked, or will it also be searchable?

Indexed resources mean there is a record created complete with metadata. Linked resources are linked to related data products, and are discoverable.

Question: Can the science areas embed the search interface?

This is a work in progress, but searches conducted will have many facets to narrow down results.

[Session notes](#)

Update on Core Services — Elena Steponaitis (NASA OCSDO) and

Andrew Mitchell (NASA OCSDO)

Highlights:

- The SMD Core Data and Computing Services Program (CDCSP) has been built out over the past year, and their team is focused on trying to facilitate a conversation within the community about developing the repository.
- The CDCSP is anticipating a data call for future data archive growth. Efforts date back to 2018 prompted by SMD strategy.
- The SMD CDCSP is presented as a service layer of SMD, and it is not projected to be at the application level. It is focused on the following efforts.
 - CDCSP has been working on executing an Architecture Study since June 2021. This effort was aimed at answering how a cloud service option may meet the needs of SMD.
 - CDCSP and Division roles will vary but are expected to be complementary and work in coordination.

Takeaways:

- CDCSP will be available to provide budget assistance. Their team will provide resources to assist with projecting associated costs.
- Looking to put out a ROSES solicitation to assist researchers, but they are not looking for vendor lock-in.
- CDCSP can be considered the liaison to assist with budgetary and contractual issues. They are actively working to establish contracts with cloud service providers. Research data and software repositories can be expected within FY24.

[Session notes](#)

Data Sharing Guidance for Researchers — Rachel Paseka (NASA OCSDO)

Rachel starts off by telling the audience the most frequent questions she gets from researchers are:

- What should we do with the data we generate if we want to send it to a repository?
- What requirements from SPD-41a affect me?
- How do I fulfill those requirements?

We have developed this guidance to help researchers on the policy requirements of SPD-41a: [Open-Source Science Guidance](#). This guidance is intended to provide SMD-funded researchers with the information they need to understand the SPD-41a requirements that apply to them and to provide suggestions for how researchers may meet the requirements. It is a plain language summary of SPD-41a requirements for researchers, and we suggest that SMD-funded researchers read the OSS Guidance rather than diving into the text of SPD-41a.

While the guidance was developed for SMD-funded researchers, some information also applies to missions. It is broad in scope for the SMD Divisions. We would like to add more discipline specific examples and case studies to help with relevancy in the future. The document has been under development for the past year and we would like it to be a living document, so we can update it as we receive more feedback from the communities. We invite input from researchers! You can [contribute on GitHub](#) or send feedback to HQ-SMD-SPD41@mail.nasa.gov

Takeaways:

- **Where to share?**
 - Data must be shared and archived to ensure accessibility and preservation of data. Repositories should meet the guidelines for SMD-acceptable data repositories in Appendix D of SPD-41a, which are based upon the [Desirable Characteristics of Data Repositories for Federally Funded Research](#). Options include (see the [Data Management and Sharing Guidance](#)):
 - i. NASA Science Data Archive. Follow any guidance in your solicitation or division, otherwise select an appropriate NASA Science Data archive (see science.data.nasa.gov).
 - ii. If there is no domain-specific repository, you may use a Generalist Repository outside of the NASA environment, it is recommended to choose one already used in your community (e.g., [Zenodo](#)).
 - iii. In some instances it is acceptable to share data as Journal Supplementary Material, but this is listed last for a reason. SMD encourages researchers to archive data in repositories, but sharing data in supplementary material may be an acceptable option as long as the data are freely accessible and machine readable.
- **How to share?**

- We will attempt for this to be more user friendly, but researchers should follow FAIR Principles when sharing data.

[Session notes](#)

Session 2 — Breakouts

After the morning session, participants worked on **two sets of three parallel breakout sessions**:

SDE/SciEx — Led by Elena Steponaitis (NASA OCSDO)

SciX will focus on the F in FAIR, indexing literature for all SMD scientific research areas. The [SAO/NASA ADS](#) (Astrophysics Data System), current precursor to SciX, links to data that is linked from literature, but it does not index the data. The SDE *will* index the data.

The SDE is expected to provide access to cross-divisional data to allow and encourage cross-divisional research. It is unclear how many researchers are doing this currently, but probably very few. In the future it should be commonplace for NASA research to be cross-divisional, but it should be easy to do. Researchers don't only need data to be Findable, but also Accessible, which will come from cloud access through NASA, at least for the large data. The scientific and technical terminology across SMD divisions is not unified, which challenges cross-divisional searches. The platforms, instruments, and missions list in SDE includes terms from all 5 SMD topical areas.

Access in the Cloud — Led by Andrew Mitchell (NASA OCSDO)

Some issues that were suggested and discussed in regards to NASA providing FAIR access to data in the cloud are listed below. These are just initial opinions from the group that resulted in the three takeaways below.

- Covering the cost of data egress (downloading) for researchers. Estimated to be 5x the cost of storage.
- While cloud computing allows some use cases that were previously not possible (computing close to extremely large datasets which are too big to download), a cloud-only solution, or a solution that requires users to work in the NASA-compatible cloud environment, disenfranchises a significant number of users who are not cloud savvy or do not need cloud services. There will need to be a balance between cloud and on-prem systems depending on the nature of the data and user community.
- Some believe that migration to the cloud will save NASA money. Some believe that is a fallacy. At least for the Earth Science Division, the data storage costs dominate the expenses, but egress is the potentially uncontrolled expense.
- Some repositories are worried that just moving all their data to the cloud would consume their budget.
- Speed of data retrieval from the cloud was reported as an issue by users.

- Moving data to the cloud represents a shift to an activity-driven cost model in operations for the repositories. For an open repository, user activity cannot be controlled, therefore the cost cannot be controlled. Under an on-premise framework, the costs were capped in the sense of capacity limits of on-premise infrastructure. Repositories need tools to manage costs in a cloud environment to stay within a predictable budget.
- How might a hybrid model work, where the bulk of downloads (e.g. of raw data) would come from non-cloud archives where the services and direct data access would be in the cloud?
- Research often requires combining NASA with non-NASA data, which is straight-forward when both are downloaded, but how would this work if NASA data must stay in the cloud?
- Do repositories need to place limits on people who are replicating their archives and block crawlers?
- Since not all users will be in the cloud, Reusability will depend on how the data is consumed. If solutions are dependent on how the data is consumed (in cloud vs outside), reusability might be limited.

Takeaways:

- The repositories will need consistent cost modeling for cloud computing; users will have different costs/needs.
- NASA leadership requires further education on when and why to go to the cloud, instead of choosing the cloud for seemingly arbitrary reasons. They need to understand the nuances to the cloud's capabilities, and maybe rethink the mandate. Moving to the cloud will not be the same across all the disciplines. Leadership should listen to the repositories and user community.
- Users and developers require consistent education, such as with analysis working group workshops. You might be getting more use out of the cloud environment, but what you're using it for might not make sense.

[Session notes](#)

Researcher Submitted Data — Led by Rachel Paseka (NASA OCSDO)

Researchers request guidance on what associated information/documents should be submitted with data to ensure reusability. It's suggested that an analog of [NASA's Earth Science Preservation Content Specification](#) would be of help. Also, the standard [ISO 19165-2](#) addresses what, when and why of various preservation content items, but these look burdensome for research data products and will need to be tailored and translated for easier consumption by researchers. There is also the question of who decides if a research product is scientifically useful and needs to be shared, and if it should be shared via a NASA repository or an external service.

Some of the issues discussed:

- How to decide where data is hosted, especially when it is multi-disciplinary? (Is there a cloud universe where it doesn't matter where data is hosted?) NASA currently suggests Zenodo as an adequate option.
 - a. Where the data is hosted in the cloud isn't as important as who is going to curate it. Metadata continues to evolve as we continue to become more interoperable.
 - b. How can archives work together so multi-disciplinary data hosted in the cloud is available to a wider audience?
- Researchers need a mechanism to see what NASA repositories are available by discipline to aid in the creation of OSDMPs.
- How to enable FAIR data at the point of ingest.
- Researchers need a more automated system to curate data, which will help the speed and volume of data we can then provide to the world to mine.
 - a. Can an automated system replace the discipline expertise offered by a data repository?
- Is an SMD-FAIR checklist plausible, or is a 'one size fits all' model not feasible due to the diversity of data?
- If researcher-produced data is to be assigned to a repository, when should it happen? When the data is ready to be archived, when the researcher is funded, or somewhere in between?
- GeneLab and ALSDA, 2 good examples where researchers can submit data; what can other disciplines model from life sciences?

Some issues/requests/comments presented by Ryan T Scott (Science Lead for the NASA Ames Life Sciences Data Archive (ALSDA), now part of the [NASA Open Science Data Repository for Life in Space](#)):

- We need better computational infrastructure with the external researchers to gather 100s of different datasets from 100s of different data producers.
- We need a more automated system (less manual) to curate the submitted data, which will help the speed and volume of data we can then provide to the world to mine.
- We need data providers to start submitting data as soon as data begins to be collected by researchers. This, opposed to gigantic data dump at the end of the experiments or end of the grant.
- Domain specificity in regards to which repository, metadata standards, what is 'FAIR', is rather important when it comes to data egress (differing tools/needs).
- The National Academies just recently released its 2023-2032 'Decadal Survey' toward BPS domain ([full report](#), [interactive summary](#), [study website](#)) entitled "Thriving in Space: Ensuring the Future of Biological and Physical Sciences Research: A Decadal Survey for 2023-2032".

One particular item that came up repeatedly throughout the session was:

- It would be useful to have a checklist for compliance of SPD-41a (also FAIR) for researcher-generated data. Would be nice to have a workflow too. Most agreed that a general "SMD SPD-41a/FAIR checklist" is not possible and it would require tailoring for each discipline/division. Or there is a common SMD-wide checklist, and in addition each

Division has their own extension to the checklist. This is further discussed in the “How to” document.

[Session notes](#)

Licenses — Led by Steve Crawford (NASA OCSDO)

The purpose of this session was to improve understanding of the data license requirements of SPD-41a.

Steve gave a basic outline and provided the following example language for repositories:

Scientific data in the [REPOSITORY] currently falls into three categorizations, when it comes to licenses:

1. The data has a license provided with it or is labeled with its license.
2. Unless the data file is marked with a restrictive notice or license, data that is provided from a NASA led mission including observations, engineering, calibration, and auxiliary data are licensed as [Creative Commons Zero](#). There are no restrictions on the usage of these data.
3. For all other data, the data are provided as is and NASA makes no warranty whatsoever or representations regarding usage. NASA may not be the original source of data and thus users are encouraged to validate the source and associated usage rights of the data.

Data providers may contact the [REPOSITORY] regarding licensing problems and revision will be reviewed for possible licensing change.

Regardless of the license, users are encouraged to cite the original source of the data and the usage of the [REPOSITORY] when appropriate.

For other material on NASA websites beyond the scientific data, please see the [NASA media usage guidance](#).

Some other clarifications emerged in the discussion.

- Federal employees cannot use CC-BY for their Federal work because they cannot hold copyright.
- CC0 does not preclude attribution or citation. In fact it encourages the use of community norms which might include attribution.
- A core purpose of licenses is to address R1.1 — (meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data usage license.
- The license must be machine readable using the CC RDFa badge or schema.org markup.
- CC-BY can inhibit reuse when machines try to automatically combine data because they don't know how to handle attribution.
- Software licensing is fundamentally different from data licensing.
- Grant-funded data is subject to the terms of the grant. Often the intellectual property of a grant is owned by the grantee institution.

- The Data Management in a proposal plan should include the type of license planned for the data.

Takeaways:

- More outreach and education on the topic for researchers and repositories are needed.

[Session notes](#)

Identity Management — Led by Elena Steponaitis and Andrew Mitchell (NASA OCSDO)

Some pros and cons of requiring identification to access repositories were presented and discussed.

Pros of identity management:

- It can mitigate misuse/misinterpretation of data.
- It allows the identification of nefarious/inappropriate use of data or systems; so the problematic activity can be turned off (on individual account case).
- It helps identify users and communicate directly with them (so that tools/services can be 'customized', for example).

Cons of identity management:

- It can introduce complexity for some communities of users.
- It can be an obstacle to FAIR.
- Custom/in-house identity management solutions may not work with vendor environments/solutions (e.g., AWS).

An important distinction in the identity management space is to separate *identity assurance* level (how confident am I that this is a real person and that the identity attributes are correct) from *authenticator assurance* level (how confident am I that this is the same entity today as it was yesterday). There are places where NASA should consider essentially pseudonymous access (low identity assurance level, but high authenticator assurance level). Identity assurance level and authenticator assurance level requirements are not a one-size-fits-all situation.

The question was asked regarding which divisions require ID/user management, and, if yes, which metrics are captured, if any:

- APD: No requirement on eligibility to access.
- ESD: Captures metrics to better target and understand users.
- BPS: Uses NASA launchpad for account management.
- HPD: No requirement to access.
- PSD: No requirement to access.

Takeaways:

- While there was no consensus on what level of identity management was necessary, all were in favor of at least some identity management for researchers using compute resources in the cloud.
- Some pointed out that instead of forcing identity management on users, the repositories should provide additional value that would entice users to register an account (dashboard with usage statistics, cost estimator calculator, technical assistance, etc).

[Session notes](#)

Streamlining Metadata Generation and Curation — Led by Rebecca Ringuette (NASA Goddard Space Flight Center) and Anne Raugh (University of Maryland)

There were several 5-minute presentations during this session:

- Rebecca Ringuette and Anne Raugh: [Streamlining Metadata Generation and Curation](#)
- Corinna Gries: [Data Curation Workflow and Tools at the Environmental Data Initiative](#)
- Danie Kinkade: [Improving Curation Efficiency at The Biological and Chemical Oceanography Data Management Office](#)
- Bob Dattore: [Metadata Curation at the NCAR Research Data Archive](#)
- Kelly Haberstroh: [Re-curating CrossRef Metadata at USGS](#)

The goal of the session was to discuss what is needed to make metadata generation and curation efficient, focusing on metadata for items submitted to support publications. The working hypothesis is that streamlining metadata intake leads to more consistent metadata, but curation of metadata, especially for legacy resources, is labor-intensive. Quality, richness, and consistency of metadata speaks directly to Findability; it also supports Accessibility and Reusability.

Takeaways:

- Journal keywords for metadata input are a first step; users want that as it will help with Findability. E.g., Earth Sciences has a list of [GCMD keywords](#) (Global Change Master Directory), and Astrophysics and Heliophysics increasingly share the [Unified Astronomy Thesaurus](#).
- When a Principal Investigator (PI) gets a grant, and the Research Data Submission Agreement (RDSA) after the Data Management Plan (DMP), the PI is encouraged to use a specific format, with an expectation on type and structure, when they go to submit their data.
- Submission forms are awful, hard to give you what you want if it's not intuitive, and they're Division specific, so one size of survey doesn't fit all. Autocomplete and suggestion features for entries would be useful, as would an interface usable by both PIs and collaborators.
- The incentive to add the metadata has to be there for the user. There are missions that don't include metadata and it's up to the repositories to add it. This problem is expected to be amplified for datasets contributed in support of publications. A Level of Service

plan for each repository, possibly similar to that in [Earth Science](#), can help navigate where efforts should be spent.

- Metadata needs to be user- and AI-ready.
- In Earth Science, DAACs use an Earthdata Publication tool that primarily helps the preparing and ingesting of data products from field campaigns and individual data providers funded by NASA. It's largely automated for front-end use across 12 DAACs and allows DAACs to plug-in DAAC-specific APIs in the backend to handle unique storage and ingest requirements.
- [Crossref](#) should be leveraged to link data and/or publications.
- Levels of curation and preservation should be considered and applied to repository data; see [Curation & Preservation Levels: CoreTrustSeal Discussion Paper](#) and the Levels of Service for [Earth Science](#).

[Session notes](#)

Day 2

Session 1 — The Principles in Detail

The first half of day 2 focused on developing guidance on how to implement the 15 specific FAIR principles. Mark Parsons began by introducing and leading a general discussion of an initial document on [“How to Make NASA Science Data more FAIR”](#). The document provides an interpretation of each principle as well as suggesting first steps and reference information for each principle. Note, the document focuses on general FAIRness across SMD. Individual divisions and repositories will need to develop more specific guidance for their disciplines. Indeed, it was generally agreed that “Interoperable” is the most difficult general principle, especially in an interdisciplinary context.

The document encourages SMD to develop practices that enable data to be “born FAIR”. That is, the data adhere to the FAIR principles at the time of creation or ingest into a management system. Different approaches will be necessary for mission data, researcher-provided data, and model output. Making legacy data FAIR will be a long, ongoing effort. Finally, the document also provides a list of general frameworks and criteria for assessing FAIRness, which were explored in more detail in one of the breakout sessions. See below.

The “How to” document will continue to evolve over time, and participants continued to make additions and revisions during and after the workshop based on the discussions during the workshop and their own experiences. The plan is to have a complete (albeit evolving) version of the document available well before the 2024 workshop.

After the introduction, participants worked in **three different breakout sessions** as follows:

Defining Roles and Incentives for Providers and Repositories — Led by Anne Raugh (University of Maryland) and Bob Downs (Columbia University)

Anne and Bob began the session with a [presentation outlining the general issue](#) indicating that the overall goal was to provide recommendations for incentivizing data producers and repositories to make their data useful, open, and FAIR, especially within the context of SPD-41a and the general move to open-source science. They highlighted some of the challenges and introduced some existing incentives particularly around credit and accountability. Kerstin Lehnert then gave a presentation on the [experience of the Astromaterials Database](#).

Group discussion led to the following synthesis:

Issue:

How can we ease the burden and provide incentives to direct some resources to making the data arriving at and curated in the repositories more FAIR? It takes additional work to make data more FAIR. This is, in general, an unfunded mandate on both data providers and repositories. This affects all aspects of FAIRness.

Takeaways:

1. Each repository has a unique relationship between itself and data providers, and itself and data users. A range of possible solutions is needed to cover the many situations, and incentives need to align with both expectations and level of effort. There is no nominal example of what a repository does.
2. Openness is going to be essential. This needs to include data quality and caveats, as well as the repository content criteria, intake processes, curation procedures, and different levels of service. This will help data providers select the appropriate repository to curate their data, as well as giving end users the information needed to determine whether a product is applicable to their planned (re)use.
3. Funders and publishers are incentivizing data producers to get DOIs, which require minimal metadata (at least), which is positively impacting “F” and “A”. In the vein of incentivizing data providers, in some cases simple, tangible recognition by the NASA repository is a highly valued reward for providing quality data. Recognizing most-used, most-cited, most-contributing, etc., provides human incentives beyond the perhaps more traditional line on a CV. Societies also have influence, in the criteria they use for honors, awards, and other forms of recognition for their members.

[Session notes](#)

FAIR Assessment Tools — Led by Rebecca Ringuette (NASA GSFC Heliophysics Digital Resource Library) and Ge Peng (UAH/MSFC IMPACT)

Rebecca introduced the session and **discussion items**:

- What FAIR assessment tools give a more complete picture of FAIR for the resource?
- Which FAIR assessment tools can be more easily plugged in at a repository as an automatic metadata ‘completeness checker’?
- What interfaces for metadata curation are easy to use and understand?
- What tools can be used to automatically add in publication DOIs into the associated items’ metadata?
- What groups are working on these topics and are willing to collaborate with others?
- What tool(s) do we recommend?

Then there were [three brief talks](#) on some existing tools and implementation experiences:

- Ge Peng: An Overview of FAIR Assessment Tools
- Dan Berrios: FAIR Assessment Approaches
- Kris Peach: FAIR Assessment Goals for OSDR

Based on these presentations, it became clear that FAIR is about data but when assessing FAIRness of data, the role of the repository is also (at least implicitly) assessed. There are multiple types of assessment including ad hoc approaches, surveys or reviews, automated approaches, and methods integrated into repository ingest workflows. They all assess somewhat different aspects of FAIRness. The DataOne approach as implemented at the Arctic Data Center was referenced as a useful “repository-integrated” model.

Lively group discussion led to the following

Takeaways:

- No FAIR assessment tools assess the same thing.
- Before we agree on an assessment tool, an SMD-wide metric should be created. The How To document is a starting point but will need more detail.
- To create the metric, we should look at what has already been done (e.g. work done by the Research Data Alliance, DataCite, and Science-on-schema.org), to make sure it fits with the federal guidelines but is general enough to apply to any science.
- There needs to be a trade study of the tools available.
- A tool needs to be created based on the SMD-wide metric and building on the efforts of tools already available to assess the FAIRness of the metadata for a given dataset, which should be extensible by repositories to incorporate their specific community standards.
- The tool should have a user-friendly interface that provides clear explanations, examples, motivation for each entry, and help via FAQs, chatbots, and NASA curators as needed.
- The tool should have different interfaces for different use cases, such as data contributors vs curators.

[Session notes](#)

Schema.org Training Session — Led by Ruth Duerr

“[Schema.org](#) data on a webpage tells search engines what your page content is about, using schemas agreed upon by publishers & consumers, for making content actionable.” Founded by

Google, Microsoft, Yahoo and Yandex, Schema.org vocabularies are developed by an open [community](#) process, using the public-schemaorg@w3.org mailing list and through [GitHub](#). Schema.org is used to mark up 10's of millions of web pages. It is increasingly being used to annotate science-related content including data sets.

Marking up data set landing pages with schema.org helps address principles F2 (data are described with rich metadata) and F4 ((meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource) and contributes to I1 ((meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation). The [Science On Schema.Org \(SOSO\) Guidance Documents](#) provide information on how to mark up data set landing pages. In this session Ruth Duerr provided a [tutorial on schema.org](#) and how to apply it for data set landing pages.

Takeaways:

- Participants found the session was good for “situational awareness.”
- Beyond having NASA index data, it would be useful if other organizations did so as well to allow users to get disciplinary data from anywhere.
- Although there are some general agreements, schema.org relies heavily on community conventions. The degree of fine-tuning available on services will depend on the agreements between end users and data providers. Depending on the agreements you can reach, you can do more or less.

[Session notes](#)

Session 2 — User Engagement

Efforts to Understand Users in the Divisions

The first segment of the session provided an opportunity for several repositories and service providers to present their successes and challenges in engaging with their user communities. Following are the speakers and their presentation titles. Their [slides are available in the session folder](#).

- Success of “analysis groups” in the Biological and Physical Systems Division, Sylvain Costes
- Machine learning exploration of literature to understand data use in heliophysics, Anthony Buonomo
- Earth Data Forum, Nate James
- International Virtual Observatory Alliance (IVOA) user engagement, Tess Jaffe and Vendana Desai
- Ring-Moon System Node User Group experience, Matt Tiscareno.

Several of the presentations (Sylvain, Tess, Vendana, and Matt) discussed their relationships with different types of user advisory groups. They varied in structure and formality, but common lessons emerged:

- Groups need to be inclusive and open. They need to be self-led to harness the passion of volunteers. In the case of BPS, they have ~600 people participating in multiple “analysis groups”.
- It works best when the groups have a particular problem to solve (e.g., a paper to write), and they work directly with the repositories to improve data and tools to solve that problem.
- Ongoing engagement and support for the group is essential through regular workshops and networking events, in person and online.
- It is challenging to broaden the diversity of research topics, especially interdisciplinary topics addressed by the user groups.

Nate James discussed how the Earth Sciences division has been working to develop a wider user discussion forum to enable communication across repositories while encouraging science and community engagement in cross-discipline areas with multi-DAAC collaboration. It is a work in progress, and requires active moderation, but participation is growing. NASA needs to consider a similar forum across all of SMD.

Anthony Buonomo demonstrated the potential for machine learning to help repositories understand how their data are being used. It shows great promise and could be broadly adaptable. Discussion continued in an unconference session on Day 3.

[Session notes](#)

User Panel

The second segment of the session was an informal panel of data users discussing their challenges and successes in accessing and using NASA data. Each participant spoke briefly on their experiences and then Demitri Muna moderated a discussion amongst the panel and with the audience. The panelists were:

- Angelle Tanner, Mississippi State, representing astrophysics users
- Ye Quanzhi, University of Maryland, planetary science
- James Casaletto, NASA Ames, biological and physical systems
- Jonathan Niehof, University of New Hampshire, heliophysics
- Eduard Heijkoop, University of Colorado, Earth science

FAIR principles are ultimately designed to increase the usefulness of data and to maximize their value in the context of research. Thus, the ultimate measure of “FAIR”-ness of infrastructure is through its use and adoption by users rather than a checklist of technical specifications. User considerations and use cases should guide the technical implementation details, not the other way around. These principles motivated inviting a panel of active researchers not affiliated with data repositories to discuss their difficulties, challenges, and use cases with respect to how they interact with repositories and consume data. The researchers were intended to be representative of multiple communities and career stages, spanning from PhD student to faculty and cutting across multiple SMD divisions. The following is a summary of challenges and findings that arose from the discussion between the user panel and the workshop participants.

A frequent comment was that data are siloed across different repositories. While this should not be a surprise (there are five divisions in the SMD but more than 30 data repositories), this has long been a burden on the user in terms of discoverability and completely different interfaces. In effect, which repository is funded to host a particular data set is an implementation detail that can hinder findability for users outside the core science team. Knowing where to find data is a steep learning curve for newer researchers and an impediment for existing ones. Correspondingly, as different repositories try and improve access for a given community it can lead to duplicate metadata and even duplicate data within and across topical areas.

Takeaways:

- Greater communication and collaboration between data repositories to more easily assist users in finding what data exist and may be relevant to their work, even if it's just pointing to another location. Support a solicitation to fund specific instances of collaboration between data repositories.

Another difficulty was in incorporating new data sets into one's research. It was noted that documentation is often aimed at those who already have high familiarity or are experts with a dataset. Related to this, it was felt that some web/user interfaces were mainly designed for the principle investigators of a dataset rather than (or at least in addition to) newer users or those from an adjacent field who may utilize them.

- Acknowledge that a wide range of experience and skill sets will be accessing data and provide more documentation and tutorials to help researchers utilize the data. This could include developing higher-level more consumable products.

Issues related to cloud computing generated a lot of discussion. Many datasets are orders of magnitude larger than one could download to a laptop. Of these, some are not yet available in the cloud which requires users to learn significant data management skills they should not be required to, or worse, leave data on the table unused. In cases where data are available on services like AWS, just having terabytes of files available does not obviate the need for a user to learn how to navigate AWS, instances, parallel multiprocessing, data management - the learning curve is quite high for researchers who are not systems architects. For example, an astronomer may need to analyze millions or billions of data points which may require an entire new skill set. Without a researcher-centric toolkit/framework, data "in the cloud" is just a larger disk. Cost related to compute, storage, and bandwidth become a big uncertainty - should additional funds be included in grant proposals or somewhere else, and how will a non-expert estimate a reasonable value? Currently funded or proposing NASA Researchers should consider taking advantage of NASA's [Science Managed Cloud Environment](#) which is trying to address some of these issues. See also further discussion on helping users (transparently) use the cloud in the unconference session on Day 3.

- While data should be made available on the cloud, users will need documentation and software frameworks to allow them to analyze the data in the cloud without the need to become system engineers. Users will need assistance in estimating, or in some cases removing the need for, additional compute cost.

It was agreed that high quality user interfaces (UIs) are extremely important, and that more focus and resources should be placed on improving them. The UI should be modeled early in the development process and lead the technical design - not be an afterthought. It was acknowledged that doing so would take actual investment in the form of graphic designers, usability studies, and regularly observing how users interact with and use the interfaces. It would require making active efforts to get feedback from the community with diverse panels, challenges, and awards; for participants this can be a resume building opportunity that drives student engagement and helps build community

- Incorporate representative users (i.e. researchers) early and often in the form of listening sessions, feedback from the community, direct observation, usage through web analytics, more and better documentation and tutorials, incentives to participate, and moderated forums.

Finally, while calls for request for information (RFIs) from NASA are a positive step in getting community feedback, it was commented that these are not reaching enough people and the wording is often unclear or confusing. The language used can impact who will reply which will impact considerations of inclusion and equality.

- Make a greater effort to reach a much wider part of the community with RFIs (or other community engagement efforts) everywhere from early to late career researchers. Text should be more clear and more attention should be paid to reach minority and other under-represented communities in RFI responses. This could be done by including science writers in the RFI creation process.

[Session notes](#)

Day 3

Unconference

Most of Day 3 was organized as an “unconference”. Over the earlier days, workshop participants posted session ideas to a shared online space. On the morning of day 3, participants voted on which sessions to conduct. Through a rather informal process combining different proposals, participants agreed to four sessions. Three sessions were conducted as breakouts:

- FAIR for Software
- Sharing of experiments or works in progress
- Large language models for curation

And the fourth session was held as a plenary discussion:

- Lowering barriers and ensuring equitable access to cloud computing and big data on demand

FAIR for Software

Rebecca Ringuette and Steve Crawford led the session.

Steve clarified issues around the NASA software release process (NPR2210) and what is being done to improve and expedite the process for open source science software. Key messages:

- If you are releasing software through NASA, start early.
- If you are a contractor, always follow contract guidance.
- The software release process does not apply to grant funding.

Rebecca then led a broader discussion of making NASA software FAIR. Participants agreed that NASA software should be searchable and therefore archived in a repository that enables broad discovery. Researchers should at least cite their own software if not also other software used in their works to increase findability. These capabilities require a metadata model to be adopted to describe software and contributions to the software (e.g. the [FAIR4RS](#) work). The session notes include multiple references to useful work conducted in these areas that could inform future work.

Takeaway:

Findability and citability are just first steps toward FAIR software and are complicated enough. This motivates the creation of a working group and workshop focused on these issues for software.

[Session notes](#)

Sharing of Experiments or Works in Progress

Bruce Wilson led the session.

Problem statement:

The Data in Scope section of SPD-41a (page10) states:

This does not include laboratory notebooks, preliminary analyses, intermediate data products, drafts of scientific papers, plans for future research, peer review reports, communications with colleagues, or physical objects, such as laboratory specimens

If SPD41a does not mean that preliminary data need to be made open, do we need to be more explicit in this assessment of sharing works in progress that it's not an SPD41a requirement to make it open (accessible) but some data producers may be interested in making preliminary data open, and then how do we support them.

The group had a rich discussion with many examples from different disciplines and scenarios that are well described in their notes. They then summarized their key findings.

Takeaways:

- There is no one size fits all answer
- More of an immediate issue for some; not clear for others when/if this will be an issue.

- SPD-41a creates the expectation that intermediate products are made available in a FAIR fashion, but there is also concern that making preliminary data available leads to increased risks of inappropriate use (see examples in the notes.)
- Intermediate data and the software that generates it are tightly linked challenges.
- Challenges finding a word that really covers this data maturity level. Definitions will be key.
- One possible approach is to give tools to the projects to make it easier for them to distribute the data, particularly since this is more of a complex issue for larger datasets (n.b. Zenodo limits to 50 GB)
- How FAIR does preliminary/intermediate data need to be? How Open should it be? How findable? Should it be findable if not ready for public use?

[Session notes](#)

Large Language Models for Curation

Alberto Accomazzi led the session.

Issue:

There are multiple ways that LLMs can be used to improve the curation and use of NASA data and there are many groups working on related issues or approaches. Is there value in coordinating these efforts?

Examples of applications include:

- Document classification for mission bibliographies: is this paper about mission X or does it use data from archive Y (e.g. SOHO classifier took 6 months to develop but is quite configurable and can be reused for other missions)
- Metadata extraction: generate structured content from unstructured content (e.g. keyword extraction from publications)
- Semantic Crosswalk across disciplines
- Suggestions for data users: if you are interested in this dataset you may also be interested in these other ones (this requires linkages between data and literature)
- Help generate coding tutorials for scientists to access archive APIs, or code auditing
- Generate list of reviewers for panels: can LLMs help in making suggestions?
- Use the LLMs as assistants to “read” papers and provide information about what data they use; don’t simply trust their output, but “reduce the haystack”

Several groups are looking at classifying papers with regard to missions/instruments. This may be a fruitful area for initial collaboration. Perhaps we can use the SMD Science LLM to solve these problems.

Takeaways:

- It would be useful to form a cross-SMD group sharing knowledge about how we can leverage these technologies since they seem applicable across the board; #IIm-for-science?

- A first project could be a general purpose tool for paper classification based on NASA data used that provides explainable results, based on a science-tuned LLM (help with curating mission bibliographies)
- Another focus could be to improve accessibility across archives via semantic crosswalks and translation across disciplines.

[Session notes](#)

Lowering Barriers and Ensuring Equitable Access to Cloud Computing and Big Data on Demand

This session was created by combining two proposals, one from Susan Mullally on “Big data and equity” and another from Heidi Kristenson on “FAIR for On Demand Products/Processing Pipelines”. The overarching theme was how to make cloud hosted data more accessible to more people, while also ensuring data remains FAIR in an on-demand environment. The discussion was open ended and broadened some of the discussion from the day 1 breakout on access in the cloud.

The Alaska Satellite Facility (ASF) has very large complex synthetic aperture radar data that has necessitated moving to the cloud. Their goal is that users don't have to know anything about cloud architecture to use the on-demand services or the OpenScienceLab platform. There were a lot of questions and answers on their experience which is well documented in the notes. Openscapes was also discussed as a helpful initiative. Other repositories see advantages to moving to the cloud but do not have demand from their users. Users however do not demand the cloud as such. They want services that solve their problems. It is the challenge for the repository to leverage the cloud to provide those services. The user need not know they are working in the cloud. Overall, the session was a useful exchange of information and experiences that we hope lead to future conversations and collaborations.

Takeaways:

- The [ROSES-23 Amendment 5: F.15 High Priority Open-Source Science](#) would be a possible mechanism for coordinating efforts on developing cloud-native processing platforms.
- FAIR Standards/Guidance is needed for on-demand products and the software used to generate them.
- Cloud computing can be a great mechanism for improving equity/access for a wide range of users, but the users shouldn't have to be cloud experts to be able to use the platforms/services provided by the repositories.

Closing

Steve Hughes gave a [closing presentation](#) rooted in information science concepts illustrating how we need to continue to build on past work. The (NASA developed) ISO standard Open Archive Information Systems (OAIS) reference model provides the meta foundation for all the

metadata required as part of FAIR. The meta-metadata if you will. This is what we need for broadly interdisciplinary connection.

Mark Parsons provided some summary remarks, thanking all the participants and the overall mission-focussed ethos of the people at NASA.

He noted that an overall theme is that researchers and repositories need more guidance. Moreover working across all the disciplines is the hardest part and we need to coordinate with work outside of NASA as well. Interdisciplinarity is really hard but it's also kind of fun. It challenges our assumptions and helps us think of new, creative solutions. Effective interfaces and documentation will be critical and that requires an organic approach that addresses specific problems of diverse users. The cloud (or clouds) are coming, but if they are to be truly useful we need to be clear about the use cases, and users will need tools, training, and clear cost scenarios.

A post workshop survey (Appendix) suggested we made good progress in meeting the goals of the workshop. Strong majorities of respondents agreed that:

- there is a more common understanding of the FAIR principles across the NASA science repositories,
- they gained useful information in making their data more FAIR and useful,
- the "How To be FAIR" document will be useful to their repository, and
- they would attend next year.

While there may be no “nominal example of what a repository does,” we do share common challenges across our diversity. Building more community across NASA repositories can only benefit us all.

Acknowledgements

Mark Parsons, JL Galache, and Demitri Muna wrote this report. It was the result of the work of many people including:

- The Program Committee who designed the agenda and identified speakers:
 - Bob Downs
 - Samrawit Gebre
 - Julie Imig
 - Lan Jian
 - Mark Parsons
 - Anne Raugh
- The Organizing Committee who worked all the logistics:
 - Molly Adams
 - Steve Crawford
 - J.L. Galache
 - Demitri Muna
 - Amanda Leon
 - Mark Parsons
 - Linda Pendergrass
- The Presenters and Session leaders who made the meeting a reality:
 - Waleed Abdalati
 - Alberto Accomazzi
 - Ashish Acharya
 - Anthony Buonomo
 - James Casaletto
 - Sylvain Costes

- Steve Crawford
- Heidi Kristenson
- Vendana Desai
- Emily Foshee
- Eduard Heijkoop
- Steve Hughes
- Tess Jaffe
- Nate James
- Andy Mitchell
- Susan Mullally
- Demitri Muna
- Kevin Murphy
- Jonathan Niehof
- Mark Parsons
- Rachel Paseka
- Elena Steponaitis
- Anne Raugh
- Rebecca Ringuette
- Angelle Tanner
- Matt Tiscareno
- Ye Quanzhi
- Bruce Wilson
- The Repository Standards and Guidelines Working Group members who designed and oversaw the overall process:
 - Lorella Angelini
 - Daniel Berrios
 - Kaylin Bugbee
 - Robert Candey
 - David Ciardi
 - Steve Crawford
 - Bob Downes
 - Robin Ferguson
 - Steve Hughes
 - Sara Lubkin,
 - Tom Morgan
 - Susan Mullally
 - Jordan Padams
 - Mark Parsons
 - Ge Peng
 - Rebecca Ringuette
 - Erich Reiter
 - Brian Thomas

Appendix — Post workshop survey results

30 Responses. Sent to 180 registrants, not all who attended the meeting. Eighty people attended in person and a variable but similar amount attended online.

Do you think there is now a more common understanding of the FAIR principles across the NASA science repositories?

Did you gain useful information on how to make your data more FAIR?

When completed, would the "How To be FAIR" document be useful to your repository?

Do you have new or improved ideas on how to engage your users?

Next year, should we include a poster session for participants to highlight their data stewardship and related activities?

Based on this meeting, would you plan to attend next year (recognizing there will be a different theme).

What suggestions do you have for improving how the meeting is organized?

1) Theme based Breakout Sessions, with Exercise/Use-Case 2) Discussion on Case-Studies and Scenario based LLM models

A cheatsheet with acronyms and even some color coding or symbology would help. Much of the meeting was incomprehensible for non-NASA attendees.

Better audio for remote attendees.

Get the date set and announced at least 6 months in advance. Preferably more. Hybrid is hard, and the only times I've seen it work well for meetings of this size, there's an audio technician in the room full-time, and that technician is managing the computer and sound board for audio integration. It is also necessary for people in the room to have access to power to allow them to help integrate on-line and in-room.

Hybrid breakout rooms were very hard to participate as a virtual attendee

I am a big fan of listening to users, and I was really looking forward to it, but I think the panel of users was not super helpful, because they represent a tiny subset of each division. Would rather get help from SMD on how to write a useful user *survey* or other ways of getting broader user feedback. There must be best practices.

I thought that the workshop was successful in identifying some of the next level issues and challenges for making FAIR understandable and useful across NASA repositories.

Make it a 2-day conference in the middle of the week -- easier to get there and back and less disruptive at home.

Meeting was organized well. Rinse, repeat...

More accessible power outlets will be nice.

Organize to include sessions like the day 2 breakout sessions.

Overall it was very successful for me. The sessions were valuable, but the hallway conversations were even more valuable to me, which is what I generally expect from this sort of meeting.

Since I am not familiar with NASA documents and data, I think the ability to learn more about the topics and acronyms before the workshop could help.

Table space and power outlet availability will be appreciated.

Test tech in advance.

The AV was really challenging, and partly as a result of that, the hybrid format didn't seem to work out well for those online. A good hybrid setup needs a lot of work and planning--for instance, the in-person attendees should be giving input via similar means to those online, and there needs to be a fair bit of structure to facilitate a truly open conversation. (The lack of power outlets also made it harder to stay in touch with the online). Discussion was split between the WebEx, the Slack, in person, and the IO Q&A.

The hybrid meeting is quite a problem for remote users to hear and know who is speaking in the non-virtual room. Recognize that it's a problem larger than this forum but would encourage planners for next years meeting to continue searching for better solution. At this point the only thing I've seen that works at all is for all the in person attendees to log in on their own laptop and interact with the meeting just like remote users. Might put a load on the local wifi so that would have to be addressed in the early planning stages but, it would solve the problem and increase inclusivity.

The more challenging part is the culture shift. People in different science divisions have been in silos for many, many years. It is difficult to change the status quo overnight.

To have slides uploaded to the program, which can be readily accessible for reference before or each day; if possible, utilize virtual reality experiences for posters or interactive platforms if the event is conducted online; consider adding online schools or training sessions to enhance the overall impact.

TOPS training should never be in-person only. I was looking forward to finally taking this at this meeting (as were other virtual participants) and was not able to do so.

We appear to behave as though all the different SMD branches are similar (in terms of their perceptions, approaches, strengths etc. specific to Open Science) when they clearly are not. We ought to clarify those differences before attempting to enforce a one-size-fits-all approach to this meeting's organization,.

What suggestions do you have for next steps to foster collaboration across repositories?

Assign activities from folks to do with each other across divisions - maybe two divisions at a time. Also like a hack-a-thon or a workshop session where we engage hands-on. I know funding is limited but it would be great to have more technical folks attend in person.

Consider longer breaks at the next meeting. The hallway track is always a valuable part for me. Support and publicize Rebecca's planned workshop on scientific software. Use the meeting notes to identify 1-3 specific collaboration activities and task someone from OCSDO to help support/facilitate/enable those collaboration activities and give that person the time to actually do that work. Plan to present on those at next year's meeting.

Coordinate with OCIO to standardize tools, practices, standards across the Agency.

Present topics which may be of interest from sessions with other data communities of practice.
Pursue potential pilots/proof of concepts projects with other centers/orgs.

Decide what are the areas where fostering collaborations make sense or not. How are we defining a repository? Clearly, we need to clarify such fundamental considerations before deciding who should collaborate with whom.

Establishing task forces or working groups to tackle key areas that are identified.

Hands-on tutorials with Jupyter Notebooks could be useful.

Has there been any discussion on the "5 to 7" concepts that might exist and that are common across the NASA repositories.

I feel like we are often preaching to the choir in these meetings.

I think this meeting is a great starting point. It would be difficult to formalize broad collaboration (it's hard enough to coordinate collaboration within divisions, let alone beyond), but this is a great way for those with similar goals to connect, and be the start of more targeted collaborations. The ROSES solicitation for cross-division collaborations is a really interesting option. Having good support for cross-division collaborative efforts would be welcome, though I wouldn't want to see that elevated to a mandate.

Identify the most urgent needs and establish cross-disciplinary task force to address them.

Incentivize collaboration across repos from top-down, providing some form of funding or credit to those repos who make their data interoperate in research projects.

Open communication channels, community of practice slack?

Perhaps monthly seminar series for archives to describe their tools and procedures.

Perhaps to form a dedicated full-time working group for the transition.

Pick themes that under active development across archives.

Provide access to instructions on how to adopt recommended SMD repository practices that can be adopted by other SMD repositories.

Regular technical tagups where challenges and possibly solutions are discussed.

Smaller thematic cross-discipline working groups.

Sponsor some visits? The European's now have a program where we can visit them and work

with their archive for a month or two.

What theme(s) should we address next year?

How to better address making data truly accessible and not just "open". How would someone working at a HBCU or community college use your repository? Invite some of these people to the meeting or seek them out in your local community.

Interoperability - collaboration across NASA repos is a form of "eating our own dog food". If we can't do it with our own data, how do we expect anyone else to do it?

Interoperability. There seemed to be consensus that this is the hardest part.

Open Source Software - Cloud Computing. These were two topics that weren't really covered in this workshop, but which had heavy participation in the unconference session.

Software.

Solutions update for issues presented this time and whether implementation of those solutions resulted in improved user experiences or streamlined DAAC services at a better cost

Trusted repositories.

User experiences.

Would like to address this in six months or so.

Any other suggestions, kudos, ideas, proposals?

Please have someone check out the functionality of the next venue. The CU local lacked accessibility on multiple fronts. But Boulder was nice!

Really liked the initial "ice breaker" exercise - great way to get people talking straight away.

Thank you!

"The unconference idea was great. This is the first of these meetings I've gone to, so I'm not sure if that's a regular feature. It would have been helpful to know a little more about the concept before the start of the meeting, and certainly going over the workflow right at the beginning of the conference would have been helpful, but it worked out fine in the end. It was great to be able to address some themes that were not included in the official conference schedule, but which clearly were of interest to many of the participants. It was unfortunate that so many people left before those sessions, but I certainly found them very valuable.

The overall program was well-designed. I liked the combination of plenary and breakouts, and it

was easy to participate. The themes were well-defined, and most of the sessions I participated in were well-moderated.

It was really an eye-opener to think outside the division I work in. Thanks to all who put so much effort into planning and executing this meeting.

We need dedicated people for these challenges due to scale issues.